

Evaluation of Issue and investment in Green Bond in India

Dr. Bageshree P. Banger Bandekar

Associate Professor
Cosmopolitan's Valia College

Mrs. Poonam D Shah

Research Scholar
D.T.S.S. College of Commerce

Abstract

Green bonds are a promising tool for mobilizing capital for climate-friendly projects. Green Bond evolved since the thematic bond market started in 2008 by World Bank through issuance of the first labelled green bond (Thapliyal S., ET, 2023). In India, Green Bond is still in its infant stage and has long life to survive. Survival of Green Bond in India highly depends on the government's role to address few challenges that need to be resolved in order to fully harness its potential. The growth of the green bond market in India will depend on a number of factors, including the level of awareness among investors, the development of clear regulations and standards, and the provision of support for green bond issuers. Indian Government has started its move to lead sustainable finance by issuing its own sovereign green bond first time in January, 2023. The global market for sustainable finance has registered considerable growth since 2014 mainly led by the issuance of green bonds (Manglunia A., ET, 2023). India in the long run will have to aim to compete globally for sustainable finance. In this research paper, researchers have tried to evaluate history of Green Bond in India to achieve better targets in future as one of the tool of sustainable finance.

Key Words: Green Bond, Sustainable Finance, Sovereign Bond, Environment, World Bank

“The only way forward, if we are going to improve the quality of the environment, is to get everybody involved.” – Richard Rogers

Introduction:

“We won’t have a society if we destroy the environment.” – Margaret Mead

Favourable climate is an essential requirement for existence of this society. But since years, human being been the main cause behind adverse alteration in climate change, major reason being burning of fossil fuels like coal, oil and gas (www.un.org). Humans have to bear the penalties of this alteration in the form of intense flood, scarcity of drinking water, wood fires, melting polar ice, rising sea levels, drought, biodiversity degradation. Each and every part of this world contributes to the emissions that cause climate change, but some countries lead others. Major seven countries leading in this emission of greenhouse gas were China, the United States of America, India, the European Union, Indonesia, the Russian Federation, and Brazil by 2020 (www.un.org.). Being leaders of climate exploitation, these countries need to be responsible for taking lead for climate protection action.

For this various frameworks, agreements and processes are defined at world level such as the Paris Agreement, the UN Framework Convention on Climate Change and the Sustainable Development Goals. Major concern is to cut emissions, adapting to climate impacts and financing required adjustments. As per UN report major countries are aiming to Net Zero Emissions by 2050. To achieve this in long term, by 2030 emissions must be cut in half by keeping boiling below 1.5°C. There is only one way to achieve this i.e. huge declines in the use of fossil fuels and mass usage of renewable energy.

Climate action calls for significant financial investment. It enforces all government authorities like banks, regulators and local bodies to expand their role to mobilize capital for low-carbon and resilient investment, managing all hurdles of major risk. However unitedly all countries decided to face this risk for better sustainable life in the green world under the leadership of United Nation through its 17 Sustainable Development Goals introduced in 2015. Implementing this since 2016, with intention of funding required climate action, 19 emerging market governments have issued Green, Social, and Sustainability bonds i.e. GSS Bonds (www.worldbank.org).

By the end of 2022, GSS bonds were issued amounting to USD 3.8 trillion. In 2022, total value of GSS bond issue reached USD 948 billion, showing 19% decrease compared to 2021. Across all different types, social bonds only witnessed largest decline in volume (-39%) in 2022

compared to 2021. (GSS Quarterly News Letter, Issue 2 of World Bank). Following figure supports the same.

Figure 1 – Global GSS Bond Annual Issuance, USD Bn Year to Date

Source: GSS Quarterly News Letter, Issue 2, World Bank

As per World Bank newsletter, sovereign issuers prefer Green Bonds the most (81% of the total issued) as reflected in below given figure. To accomplish green and sustainable projects, As of January 2023, Green Bonds have raised total \$2.5 Trillion globally. (www.worldbank.org)

Figure 2 - Sovereign GSS issuance by type of instrument, % year to date

Source: GSS Quarterly News Letter, Issue 2, World Bank

Following so many regulations by International Organisations such as United Nations and World Bank at world level, India also must had taken actions to develop sustainable finance at national level. In this research paper, researchers tried to undertake study to understand and evaluate steps taken by Indian government in this path.

Review of Literature:

According to ICMA, “Green Bonds are any fixed income financial instruments where the proceeds will be exclusively used to finance (or re-finance) new (and/or existing) green projects where green projects are related to the followed field: Renewable energy, energy efficiency, pollution prevention, clean transportation, sustainable water management, etc.” (ICMA 2018, Green Bond Principles). Cortellini G. & Panetta I. (2021), highlight roots of green bond. CBI (Climate Bond Initiative) and ICMA are two Non-Profit Organisations (NPO) at international level diverting efforts to mobilize capital flows for projects contributing to green climate. These organisations are working towards providing market intelligence, standards, and policy recommendations, assisting all security markets participants to accentuate good practices and standards in the market. In July, 2013; the first issuer of municipal green bond was the state of Massachusetts in the USA. In November, 2013; the ‘Electricite de France’ was the first corporate green bond issuer. (Jones et al. 2020) highlighted that in 2013 itself, various green bond market indices were launched to sign the market progress contributing to the development of the market. Ehlers T. & Packer F. (2017) attested that issuance of labelled green bonds has increased rapidly from January 2014 after the International Capital Market Association (ICMA) the launched Green Bond Principles. With increasing reach there is high need of credit ratings of the same. Green bond standards could be enhanced further by incorporating estimation of the degree of financial risks restricting from environmental factors. Ning Y et al. (2023) highlighted that Value-at-Risk is defined at a global level a new concept of Energy Budgets at Risk (EBaR) is developed for building efficiency project risk and return analysis for financial decision-makers. It was recommended by government of respective countries to incorporate Value-at-Risk-type energy efficiency analysis in utility, state, and federal incentive programs. Agarwal S. & Singh T. (2018) approved that Indian Green Bond Market has not yet succeeded to put its feet in the Indian financial market. In 2013, with introduction of the Green Bond Principle (GBP), the market responded positively. Green Bond Principal is a voluntary process to recommend guidelines for transparency and disclosure and promote integrity for the development of the Green Bond market. It gives guidelines for standardized issue process. Over the years after GBP, India has developed several standards and models to fill the gap of evaluation of environmental credentials of bonds. Kumar S. (2022) backing that India has lot of potentials for the development of green bond market. Fast developing economy, adaptive & transformative financial sector, fast spreading global linkages, playing prominent role in global

policymaking creates favourable financial environment for growth of flourishing Green Bond Market.

Objectives of the study:

This research was undertaken by the researchers to achieve following objectives-

1. To understand the structure of green financing initiatives in India.
2. To evaluate investment pattern of financing of Green Bond in India.
3. To examine various challenges in the Indian Green Bond Market.

Research Methodology:

This study is based on secondary data collected from various reports published by regulatory organisations and authorities at national and global level such as Government of India, World Bank, reports of public and private sector organisations and banks in India, United Nations, and various research papers.

Evaluation of Green Bond in India:

India, though accounts for only 7% of the world's greenhouse gas emissions, but committed to take bold steps to decarbonize its economy. (CFLI India, 2023). India through its National Determined Contribution (NDC) adopted under Paris Agreement, now committed to reduce its emission intensity of its GDP by 45% by 2030 from 2005 level and further it is committed to reduce its cumulative electric power installed capacity by 50% , from non-fossil fuel-based energy resources by 2030 (www.dea.gov.in). India has already invested close to \$87 billion in its renewable energy sector in last 10 years and presently, according to Bloomberg, an investment opportunity of \$ 650 billion is available in India's power sector transition across generation, storage, and grid infrastructure, according to Bloomberg. Private capital will be crucial, in addition to available public and existing finance, to deliver these investments (CFLI India, 2023).

To achieve this, many schemes and programmes has commenced by Indian Government in many sectors like forest, energy and enterprise, agriculture, waste management, sustainable mobility and housing, water, , resource efficiency and circular economy. . All these is estimated with additional investment of \$380 billion by India's Ministry of New and Renewable Energy (MNRE). For the growth of the renewable energy sector in India and to reach its renewable energy goals, long-term, low-cost debt capital is very critical., The U.S. Agency for

International Development (USAID) between 2013 to 2017 associated itself with the MNRE to find financing mechanisms that are innovative and it can help to overcome the market's financial limitations (ww.usaid.org). To fund all these sustainable development projects, India was highly self-reliant. But it requires collective efforts of government entity, public sector & private sectors. Following figure gives detail information on parties involved actively to boost Indian Green Bond Market as the same is applicable at a global level.

Figure 3 – The investment chain: The interaction of the private sector, public sector, & real economy

Source: <https://www.bloomberg.com/cfli/impact/#1669142365796-a14fca09-ff28>

Banking system in India should promise faster growth of the green bonds market as it is established with vibrant securities markets. India’s regulatory structure is well developed and enabling seamless integration with global regulatory templates and standards will help to successfully harness the potential of emerging market segments.

In 2015, India move in the green bond market (GBM) after YES Bank issued the first green bond to finance the renewable and clean energy projects. Gradually, the GBM has increased its operations to Government owned Commercial Banks, Government owned Financial Institutes, PSU’s private corporates, and the banking sector. India ranks fifth among G20 Countries in Green Bond issuance as a share of country’s overall debt market, As per The Climate Transparency’s Brown to Green Report 2017.

Figure 4 – Green Bond Issuance of G20 Countries

Source: Climate Transparency Group, G20 Brown to Green Report, 2017

This attests the position of Indian Green Bond Market in 2017 and future scope in the country. Issue of Sovereign Green Bonds to achieve its mark of significant reduction in the carbon intensity of the economy was announced in The Union Budget 2022-23. On 25 January, 2023 **India** came up with its launch of first green bond to raise about INR 8000 Crore , maturing 5 and 10 years for projects which are contributing to climate change mitigation, adaption environmental protection, biodiversity, resource and net zero objectives. (www.dea.gov.in). It was oversubscribed for more than four times. On 9 February, 2023 issue was reopened for INR 4000 Crore increasing India’s green liabilities to INR 16000 Crore (www.rbi.org.in). The proceeds from this have been earmarked for use of expenditures on various projects such as

solar energy use, and wind energy from agriculture to industry. It also gets extended to green hydrogen, metro lines and afforestation. (Initiative Climate Bond, 6 March, 2023).

Figure 5 – India’s Annual Green Bond Issuance

Source: TOI, 14 June, 2023

India is the sixth largest issuer of GSS+ in the Asia Pacific Region, as per the World Bank (IBRD) Impact Report, 2022. However, adverse macroeconomic factors observed in 2022 resulted into a drip in debt volumes across the board.

Figure 6 – Green Bond Commitment by Country & Sector

Source: The World Bank (IBRD) Impact Report, 2022

Strong demand for Indian currency Green Bond was observed from domestic investors. This can be an attraction for private sector players to enter into the sustainable finance market. Before entry of major private players, stringent regulations are required in India to march in its sustainable investment growth nationally & internationally.

Figure 7 – Sector wise issue of Green Bond in India

Source: World Bank with data from Bloomberg

Sovereign green bonds definitely going to play a major role in auxiliary India's green transition to achieve its adapted targets of falling emissions by 2030 and achieving zero emission by 2070. In spite of good pick up of Indian Green Bond Market, the pace of growth in this direction is very slow. Few challenges still faced are –

1. Existence of lot of misconception about understanding, regulations and benefits of Green Bond
2. Lot of compliance concerns and lack of investor demand
3. Absence of strong supportive regulatory environment
4. High issuance cost
5. Lack of Transparency, standardized reporting and independent third-party verification

Recommendation & Conclusion:

Based on the evaluation of Indian Green Bond Market as mentioned above, researchers have few recommendations for future growth of Indian Green Bond Market. It is as follows-

- Innovated features in Green Bond such as flexibility in duration of investment for investor

- Credit Ratings for green bond
- Encouragement to domestic institutional investor for widening investor base
- Bench Marking with some other government securities
- Stringent guidelines for issuance and listing of green bond in local market
- Generating awareness through publicity through traditional and modern means of social media
- Application of certifications for professionals involved in management of green bonds
- Special education through specific programmes directing to sustainable finance or green bonds markets
- Encouraging more research in sustainable finance arena

If governing body takes up few of the above recommendations, Indian Green Bond market can be one of the strong thread of sustainable finance.

References:

- Abhilash, Shenoy, S. S., Shetty, D. K., Lobo, L. S., & N, S. K. (2023). Green Bond as an Innovative Financial Instrument in the Indian Financial Market: Insights From Systematic Literature Review Approach. *SAGE Open*, 13(2), 21582440231178783. <https://www.bloomberg.com/cfli/mobilizing-investment/india/>
- Agarwal, S., & Singh, T. (2018). Unlocking the green bond potential in India. <http://hdl.handle.net/2451/42243>
- Cortellini, Giuseppe, and Ida Claudia Panetta (2021) Green Bond: A Systematic Literature Review for Future Research Agendas. *Journal of Risk and Financial Management* 14: 589. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jrfm14120589>
- Ehlers, Torsten and Packer, Frank, Green Bond Finance and Certification (September 17, 2017). *BIS Quarterly Review* September 2017, Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3042378>
- Gupta, A. R., & Bonds, G. (2020). Financing India's renewable energy vision. *ORF Issue Brief*, 336
- Kumar, S. (2022). Critical assessment of green financing initiatives in emerging market: A review of india's green bond issuances. *Academy of Marketing Studies Journal*, 26(5), 1-14.

- Nassiry, D. (2018). *Green bond experience in the Nordic countries* (No. 816). ADBI Working Paper.
- Verma, A., & Agarwal, R. (2020, April). A study of green bond market in India: A critical review. In *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering* (Vol. 804, No. 1, p. 012052). IOP Publishing.
- <https://economictimes.indiatimes.com/markets/bonds/unlocking-full-potential-of-green-bonds-in-india/articleshow/101541808.cms>
- <https://www.mdpi.com/1911-8074/14/12/589>
- <https://www.un.org/en/climatechange/science/key-findings>
- <https://www.usaid.gov/energy/sure/indian-green-bonds>
- <https://www.worldbank.org/en/news/feature/2023/04/10/from-india-to-indonesia-green-bonds-help-countries-move-toward-sustainability>
- https://www.undp.org/sustainable-development-goals?gclid=CjwKCAjw8ZKkBhArEiwAspcJ7jLxBb-JvGCVKXYDddjUFoK2jkYKzS5wbEji5LclbjeW12cRZ0jQUxoCdT0QAvD_BwE
- <https://thedocs.worldbank.org/en/doc/98c3baab0ea4fc3da4de0e528a5c0bed-0340012023/original/GSS-Quarterly-Newsletter-Issue-No-2.pdf>
- Director of economic affairs, <https://dea.gov.in/sites/default/files/Framework%20for%20Sovereign%20Green%20Bonds.pdf>
- Climate Bonds India, <https://www.climatebonds.net/2023/03/india%E2%80%99s-debut-sovereign-green-bond-market-first-deal-landed-greenium>